

QUALIFIED STAFF IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM PREPARATION STRATEGY

Fergana Polytechnic Institute

Assistant **B. Arzimatov**

Annotation: The development of tourism remains one of the priority tasks in the new Uzbekistan, which is striving to accelerate the pace of economic development. From this point of view, the determination in the New Uzbekistan Strategy that "issues such as personnel training and skill development for the sector will be in the center of our attention" indicates that it is an expression of large-scale reforms being implemented in our country. The experience of the world tourism industry shows that the elimination of problems related to personnel in the tourism sector is undergoing quantitative and qualitative changes. In this article we can data about qualified staff in the field of tourism preparation strategy.

Keywords: Tourism, research, strategies, qualified staff, development, economy, advanced facilities.

The results of our research showed that in the third millennium, there will be a high demand for tourism products that provide the most satisfaction for a short period of time. Uzbekistan has all the necessary resources for the development of tourism: there are ancient historical architectural monuments, monuments of folk art, nature reserves, mountain and water tourism, etc. In the development strategy of Uzbekistan until 2035, the share of tourism in GDP is expected to increase from 1.4% to 28%.

It is also worth mentioning that Uzbekistan has a huge potential for the development of this sector. Therefore, the development process of tourism in the country will accelerate in the future, and as a result, it will become one of the leading sectors of the economy. But solving such urgent tasks is influenced by several factors. One of these factors is "workforce", "tourist worker", "tour operator", "guide" which

is located in the center of tourist resources, ultimately called "personnel". Its past, present state, prospects for improvement in the future, scientific-theoretical research in all directions, including the topic we have chosen, are closely related to the concept of "highly qualified personnel in the field of tourism". Because in scientific research in this direction, the concept of "highly qualified personnel in the field of tourism" is of primary and decisive importance compared to all other categories and concepts. For example, it is impossible to evaluate the quality of "tour operator" or "guide" tourist services without fully understanding the essence of the concept of "highly qualified personnel in the field of tourism", without giving it a thorough and complete definition. Also, researching the state of its preparation, determining the development trends of its organizational and economic mechanism, and forecasting development prospects depend on the correct interpretation of the concept of "highly qualified personnel in the field of tourism". The role of highly qualified personnel in the tourism sector in the tourism economy, the employment of tourist workers,

As we mentioned above, the training of highly qualified personnel is of great importance in accelerating the economic development of the society. In practice, they are a tool, a means of increasing economic efficiency by increasing profits. A tourist enterprise (tour operator and travel agency) operating in the environment of intense competition in the tourism market, as a result of hiring highly qualified personnel, develops a new tourist route, reduces costs, increases the volume of tourism products per unit of time, creates additional amenities for tourists and other activities. can maintain and strengthen its position in the market. This ultimately ensures higher profitability in the network.

When it comes to highly qualified personnel in the field of tourism- intellectual potential, skills and professional skills, the ability to forecast and adequately assess socio-economic situations, a systematic approach to the management of the tourist process is understood as a tourist employee who has the competence of competence and organizes labor activities within the norms of the modern requirements of the tourism industry. When it comes to highly qualified personnel in the field of tourism-

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In short, the training of personnel in the field of tourism remains one of the ultimate goals of our country. Nevertheless, expanding the study and exchange program of students in the higher education system with countries that are currently leading in the field of tourism in the foreign education system, developing a program to "work and travel" for more internships or internships during the summer vacation, and it would be appropriate to connect the leading tourism organizations in our country, to launch the 50/50 program, and to update the training system of tourism personnel, giving them the opportunity to study for 3 days and work for 3 days. In the future, the development of mature personnel will depend on the steps taken from now on.

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